

On the importance of mooring system parametrisation for accurate floating structure designs

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Abstract

This paper analyses the importance of mooring design parametrisation on the dynamic behaviour of mooring loads. An exhaustive sensitivity analysis is performed to evaluate the variability of mooring loads because of inaccuracies in the definition of model inputs, including physical and numerical parameters. Results show a relevant dependence on the length and significance in other parameters, such as the weight together with the hydrodynamic equivalent diameter and the drag forces. An inaccuracy below 1 % in the mooring reference length can generate loads of up to twice the design, and an incorrect definition of the weight or the drag coefficient in the mooring design can lead to a design load variability of up to 30 %. Stiffness plays a crucial role in snap events, reaching load differences of 19 % depending on the stiffness selected.

This research is based on a set of numerical models capable of predicting the mooring system response. A dynamic numerical model with two schemes of resolution is implemented and calibrated according to an experimental test campaign. Other sources of results provided by a quasi-static model and commercial software, Sesam (DNV-GI), are incorporated. In general, the dynamic numerical models show a good accuracy with an experimental database composed by a set of 2D prescribed movement tests at the fairlead of the mooring system.

Keywords: Mooring, Experimental, Numerical, Validation

1. Introduction

The mooring system is an important element for floating offshore structures, having a significant influence on the global response of the structure in terms of movements and loads [1]. The compliance of the mooring system is frequently evaluated by means of extreme loads (Ultimate Limit State) and fatigue damage (Fatigue Limit State) [2] [3]. Hence, mooring numerical models are an important design tool for obtaining an accurate prediction of these loads and evaluating the performance of the floating structure.

Different numerical models have been proposed to simulate the behaviour of mooring lines in a catenary configuration. The quasi-static approach assumes that the line is in static equilibrium at each time step, neglecting the dynamic effects. Therefore, this approach is based on catenary analytical equations [4]. The main disadvantage of this method is the omission of the hydrodynamic forces and the inertial terms, which are important when evaluating the mooring dynamics. A more complex range of dynamic models, based on Newton's 2nd law of motion, have been developed since the first work of Walton et al. [5]. These may include different numerical schemes [6], such as: finite difference methods [5], lumped mass methods [7] [8] or finite element methods [9] [10] [11] [12] [13].

Walton et al. [5] described the mathematical problems related to the resolution of the system of non-linear partial differential equations governing the motion of a cable that are solved by finite difference methods. Leonard et al. [14] theoretically examined the basic foundations, similarities and fundamental differences between the finite element methods and the lumped parameter methods. Garret [15] developed a finite element method for slender rods comparing the numerical results with exact solutions for certain nonlinear problems. Triantafyllou [16] exhaustively described cable mechanics for marine applications, including the catenary configuration and its applications, dynamics of cables and the design of mooring systems. According to existing literature, the most relevant numerical models currently available for solving the equation of motion of a cable while neglecting bending and torsional stiffness are based on the finite element and lumped mass methods. Hall et al. [8] developed a lumped mass approach, including axial elasticity, hydrodynamic loading by means of Morison's equation and sea bottom contact. This model was successfully validated against data from a scale model floating offshore wind turbine test. Comparisons between computational models and laboratory tests for a mooring line with prescribed harmonic displacement have been described by different authors. Van den Boom [17] found a good correlation between the measured and calculated line tensions during the harmonic oscillation tests for different frequencies and depths using a lumped mass model. Vassalos et al. [10] established the non-linear equation

for the vertical motion of the cable and solved it using the Galerkin method. This code was compared with experimental results. The marine cable was suspended with its two ends on the same level. Different motions with known amplitudes and frequencies were applied by restraining one end of a horizontally placed cable and exciting the other end in the horizontal direction. A good agreement was achieved between the numerical and experimental results. Simos et al. [18] validated the Orcaflex numerical model [19] against experimental tests using prescribed harmonic motions in pitch with different combinations of amplitude and frequency. Their experiments included a model of a chain – steel wire rope – chain line and a current profile. A good agreement between the simulations and experiments was reached. Palm et al. [11] developed a finite element code based on the hp formulation of the discontinuous Galerkin method. An hp formulation is an adaptive numerical scheme to dynamically change the mesh size h and the polynomial order p . The hallmark of this method is that the solutions are allowed to be discontinuous over elemental boundaries and that the elements are coupled by numerical fluxes, as in the finite volume method. The code was validated with experimental tests previously published by Lindahl [20]. The experiments used a chain submerged in a concrete wave tank with the fairlead attached to a circular plate with a fixed rotation speed in the pitch position. The plate was excited in a vertical circular motion with different radii and periods. A good agreement between the computed and measured tensions was achieved. Recently, Azcona et al. [7] presented a study of the dynamics of a mooring line, implementing different setups of a catenary and prescribed harmonic motions in the surge direction. A successful validation of a code based on a lumped mass formulation was obtained in terms of tensions, which included the slack tension events as well as motions recorded at different points located along the mooring line. Aamo et al. [12] [13] developed a finite element model for a cable suspended in water. The hydrodynamic loads on the cable were modelled according to Morison's equation. However, the internal damping and friction were neglected.

All the previous researchers listed above have highlighted the need for using non-linear codes to evaluate the dynamic behaviour of mooring systems after validating their results with laboratory tests. An important source of non-linearity in moorings is due to the fluid drag. Moorings may become slack under periodic environmental excitations. In this case, the motion of the mooring is dominated by inertia and drag forces, which can be operating in alternating taut-slack conditions. These conditions cause high tension in the mooring with risk of breakage and another additional non-linearity due to the mooring stiffness needs to be considered. Finally, Gobat et al. [21] noted that the touch-down region where the mooring hits the sea floor is another external force discontinuity. Despite this phenomenon, he demonstrated the accuracy

of considering an elastic foundation approach to simulate the bottom interaction, even with tension discontinuities. According to existing literature, a wide variety of dynamic codes with different numerical schemes have been developed for assessing the mooring loads. All these models have been validated based on laboratory tests to evaluate their reliability in the prediction of loads. However, there are limited analyses on the different parameters involved in mooring numerical models, which may compromise their outcomes. Numerical parameters such as damping or number of elements may have an important influence on the mooring behaviour. Other parameters need to be calibrated to reliably reproduce the mooring dynamics. Friction models involve variables referred to seabed that are generally a source of uncertainty. Deformable and non-deformable seabed need to be investigated to propose representative friction parameters. Finally, other parameters present a wide range of variability as stated by standards. Drag and added mass coefficients may be limited depending on the mooring dynamics.

The novelty of this paper is to explore the role of mooring design parameters on load prediction. A sensitivity analysis against a comprehensive laboratory testing database [24] is conducted to evaluate the impact of each design parameter on the load estimation. Therefore, the experimental database constitutes a benchmark to evaluate not only the importance of mooring design parameter but also the accuracy of the numerical models that are described in this work.

To achieve the objective of this research work, a dynamic mooring numerical code is developed and implemented. The finite element code proposed here is based on Aamo et al. [12] [13]. The new development includes some improvements over Aamo et al., such as internal damping and the seabed friction model. The internal damping on the mooring line physically simulates the effects of friction between links of chain and is a numerically important element for contributing to the numerical stability. The seabed friction simulates the contact between the mooring line and the floor. The bottom contact is modelled by a spring and damper following the initial approach proposed by Webster [22] and has been implemented in other numerical codes [7] [8] [11] [19] [21]. Two numerical schemes have been implemented to solve the equation of cable dynamics. One of them solves the complete matrix of the system, requiring a larger computational cost. The other one transforms the complete matrix into a tridiagonal matrix simplifying the system solving. To evidence the impact of the simplifications on the results, this work also makes use of other sources of results by using a quasi-static model [4] and a commercial model called Sesam from DNV [23]. Finally, the different mooring numerical approaches

aforementioned in the previous paragraph are validated with experimental tests under different prescribed motions at the fairlead for a submerged catenary in a flume according to [24].

The paper is organised as follows. Section 2 provides the mathematical and scientific basis of the implemented mooring numerical models. Section 3 describes the experimental case while the parameters selected for the numerical models are presented in section 4. Section 5 presents the validation of the numerical models developed, as well as the verification with the quasi-static model and the Sesam software. Also, a sensitivity study is included to evaluate the importance of each parameter on the mooring behaviour. Finally, the paper is closed with some conclusions.

2. Equations of governance. Solving schemes: quasi-static and dynamic models

2.1 Quasi-static model

The quasi-static model is based on assuming the catenary equation to be stationary at each time step. To apply this model to the study of a mooring system, some assumptions must be made:

- (1) Horizontal seabed.
- (2) The cable is in a vertical plane within the x-z plane.
- (3) Bending stiffness is neglected. This hypothesis is a good approximation for chains, even with a small radius of curvature. However, when bending must be considered, the results provided by the model will be less accurate.
- (4) Dynamic effects in the line will be neglected.

Results are only a function of the instantaneous horizontal and vertical distances between the anchors and fairleads, and the mooring line characteristics. An iterative Newton-Raphson method is used to compute the solution at each time step. Its main advantage is its efficiency. The analytical equations of the mooring line geometry (x,z) and the tension [4] with seabed interaction are summarised in equation (1).

$$\begin{aligned}
x(s) & \begin{cases} s, 0 \leq s \leq L_B - \frac{H_F}{C_B \rho_0} \\ s + \frac{C_B \rho_0}{2EA} \left[s^2 - 2 \left(L_B - \frac{H_F}{C_B \rho_0} \right) s + \left(L_B - \frac{H_F}{C_B \rho_0} \right) \text{MAX} \left(L_B - \frac{H_F}{C_B \rho_0}, 0 \right) \right], L_B - \frac{H_F}{C_B \rho_0} \leq s \leq L_B \\ L_B + \frac{H_F}{\rho_0} \ln \left[\frac{\rho_0 (s - L_B)}{H_F} + \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{\rho_0 (s - L_B)}{H_F} \right)^2} \right] + \frac{H_F s}{EA} + \frac{C_B \rho_0}{2EA} \left[-L_B^2 + \left(L_B - \frac{H_F}{C_B \rho_0} \right) \text{MAX} \left(L_B - \frac{H_F}{C_B \rho_0}, 0 \right) \right], L_B \leq s \leq L \end{cases} \\
z(s) & = \begin{cases} 0, 0 \leq s \leq L_B \\ \frac{H_F}{\rho_0} \ln \left[\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{\rho_0 (s - L_B)}{H_F} \right)^2} - 1 \right] + \frac{\rho_0 (s - L_B)^2}{2EA}, L_B \leq s \leq L \end{cases} \\
T(s) & = \begin{cases} \text{MAX} (H_F + C_B \rho_0 (s - L_B), 0), 0 \leq s \leq L_B \\ \sqrt{H_F^2 + (\rho_0 (s - L_B))^2}, L_B \leq s \leq L \end{cases}
\end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where s denotes the longitudinal coordinate, C_B the static friction coefficient, ρ_0 the linear weight of the line, E the Young's module, A the sectional area, L_B the unstretched length of a mooring line resting on the seabed, L the total unstretched length of a mooring line, H_F the horizontal component of the tension at the fairlead, x the horizontal distance between the anchor and a point on a mooring line, z the vertical distance between the anchor and a point on a mooring line and T the tension at a point on a mooring line.

2.2 Dynamic model

An alternative to the quasi-static model is to use a dynamic model, [7] [8] [9] [11] [12] [13]. This alternative can be performed by studying a flexible cable by means of a one-dimensional, second order, non-linear wave equation. The hydrodynamic loads on the cable are modelled according to Morison's equation. The cable is assumed to be perfectly flexible, considering the bending and torsional stiffness to be negligible. This hypothesis is especially suitable when the mooring is made up of chain links.

Denoting the 3D position of the catenary by \vec{r} , the longitudinal coordinate by s , the Young's module by E , the sectional area of the cable by A , the linear weight of the cable by ρ_0 , the strain by e and the external forces on the cable by \vec{f} , then the equation describing the cable dynamics is given by:

$$\rho_0 \frac{\partial^2 \vec{r}}{\partial t^2} = \frac{\partial}{\partial s} \left(\frac{T}{1+e} \frac{\partial \vec{r}}{\partial s} \right) + \vec{f}(1+e) \tag{2}$$

In the present numerical model, the tension, T , includes an internal damping based on the Rayleigh model related to the deformation velocity ($\partial e / \partial t$).

$$T(t, s) = EA \left(e + \beta \frac{\partial e}{\partial t} \right) \quad (3)$$

where β is the internal damping coefficient. Internal damping is included when the lumped mass model (LM) is used to solve equation (2), [7] [8], but it is ignored ($\beta = 0$) when the finite element method (FEM) is applied [11] [12] [13].

The external forces (\vec{f}) are composed of the buoyancy force (\vec{f}_{hg}), the components of the hydrodynamic drag forces, normal (\vec{f}_{dn}) and tangential, (\vec{f}_{dt}), the hydrodynamic inertial force (\vec{f}_i) and the seabed contact force (\vec{f}_{sb}). Their formulations are given by the following equations (4) - (8):

$$\vec{f} = \vec{f}_{hg} + \vec{f}_{dn} + \vec{f}_{dt} + \vec{f}_i + \vec{f}_{sb} \quad (4)$$

- Gravity and the hydrostatic force. It is assumed that each element of the cable is completely surrounded by water. This term accounts for both the weight and the buoyancy of the cable together:

$$\vec{f}_{hg} = \rho_0 \frac{\rho_c - \rho_w}{(1 + e) \rho_c} \vec{g} \quad (5)$$

where ρ_c is the cable density, ρ_w the water density and \vec{g} the gravitational acceleration.

- Drag force. Morison's equation is considered to account for the drag forces, viscosity, around the cables, which can be considered a slender cylinder:

$$\vec{f}_{dn} = -\frac{1}{2} C_{DN} d \rho_w |\vec{v}_n| \vec{v}_n; \quad \vec{f}_{dt} = -\frac{1}{2} C_{DT} d \rho_w |\vec{v}_t| \vec{v}_t \quad (6)$$

where C_{DN} and C_{DT} are the normal and tangential drag coefficients, respectively, d is the cable diameter, and \vec{v} is the fluid velocity. The subscripts n and t denote their decompositions into the normal and tangential velocity components, respectively.

- Hydrodynamic inertial force. This force accounts for the inertia of the water displaced by the movement of the cable:

$$\vec{f}_i = -C_I \frac{\pi d^2}{4} \rho_w \vec{a}_n \quad (7)$$

where C_I is a hydrodynamic mass coefficient, \vec{a} is the fluid acceleration, and \vec{a}_n denotes its normal projection.

- Seabed contact force. This force accounts for the presence of the seabed, which avoids the catenary progressing below it. This contact is simulated with a spring and a damper in the normal direction, $\vec{f}_{sb,n}$, [8] and a tangential friction model in the horizontal direction [7] [11], $\vec{f}_{sb,t}$.

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{f}_{sb,n} &= d[(z_{bot} - r^z)K_G - \dot{r}^z K_B]r^z \\ \vec{f}_{sb,t} &= -f_{hg}K_\mu \min\left(\frac{\dot{r}^{xy}}{v_\mu}, 1\right) \frac{\dot{r}^{xy}}{\|\dot{r}^{xy}\|} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where z_{bot} is the vertical coordinate of the seabed, r^z is the vertical projection of position vector and \dot{r}^z is its velocity. The constants K_G and K_B represent the stiffness and viscous damping coefficients, respectively. K_μ is the coefficient of kinetic friction corresponding to a maximum velocity v_μ and \dot{r}^{xy} represents the velocity of the horizontal projection of the position vector.

Using the FEM [12] [13] or the LM [7] [8], the partial derivative equation (PDE) (2) is discretised in $n+1$ points ($\vec{r} = [r_0, r_1, r_2, \dots, r_{n-1}, r_n]$), where r_0 is the anchor position, fixed, and r_n is the position of the fairlead at the body, which moves with the body. The equation can be transformed into a system of $3(n + 1)$ second order ODEs. Since the movement of the body is known r_n is not an unknown and can be removed from the system. The anchor is represented by r_0 , and it is assumed that it does not move, so it can also be removed from the system, resulting in a system of $3(n - 1)$ second order ODEs. This second order system of ODEs can be transformed into a system of first order ODEs with twice the number of unknowns using a simple change of variables.

The numerical model implemented in this work is based on the FEM proposed in [12]. In that work, the following approximation is also proposed to simplify the implementation:

$$\dot{r}_{k-1} \approx \dot{r}_k, \dot{r}_{k+1} \approx \dot{r}_k, \ddot{r}_{k-1} \approx \ddot{r}_k, \ddot{r}_{k+1} \approx \ddot{r}_k \quad (9)$$

This approximation simplifies the matrix of the system so the full matrix is transformed to a tridiagonal matrix. Therefore, the system of equations can be solved at each time step using the Thomas algorithm [25], which is computationally very efficient. As it was previously mentioned, this work includes two implementations: one considering and one without considering the approximation proposed by [12]. The result of the second approach is a system of ODEs with a bounded matrix, where the system is solved using LAPACK routines [26] with the drawback of a larger computational cost. The developed model can combine different line characteristics along the same line as well as different spaces between nodes. This combination is a different feature with respect to other codes [7] [8] [11] [12]. The resulting first order ODEs system is then solved in this work using the library ODEPACK [27]. The available methods comprise both predictor-corrector Adams method, which are recommended for non-stiff problems, and methods based on the Backward Differentiation Formula (BDF), which are recommended for stiff problems. These methods use a variable time step and perform a convergence test to compute the appropriate new time interval. The tolerances applied in this work for the convergence of new time steps are very restrictive, with a relative tolerance of 10^{-7} and an absolute tolerance of 10^{-9} , to ensure the correct solution of the system.

Finally, a commercial software called Sesam is used to compare the numerical codes previously described. Sesam [23] is a package of numerical tools used to predict the interaction between waves and marine structures. It is widely used in the development and certification of offshore platforms. The simulations presented here have been performed using the following modules: GeniE for the structural design and HydroD and DeepC for the hydrodynamic analysis in the frequency domain and time domain, respectively.

3. Description of laboratory test model

The data used in this study comes from an exhaustive test campaign presented in [24]. However, a brief description is given next. A set of model scale tests of three different mooring line specimens were performed at the Environmental Hydraulics Institute of Cantabria (IHCantabria) in a catenary configuration. This work only examines the tests performed at a 1:40 scale using the heaviest mooring line. The properties of the mooring line are presented in Table 1. It has a length of 7.305 m, including the load cell. A spring was added to simulate the prototype stiffness at the end of the mooring line. However, the

mooring line was never taut under the tested laboratory movements. For this reason, the stiffness used only takes the contribution provided by the chain and measured through tensile tests into account. The line is made up of a steel chain with a link diameter of 3 mm. All results presented in this paper are at the model scale unless otherwise stated.

Table 1. Properties of the mooring line measured at laboratory (Model scale based on Froude scaling)

PROPERTIES	
Link diameter (mm)	3
Length (m)	7.305
Weight (kg/m)	0.162
Water depth (m)	1.35
Position of fairlead below the water surface (m)	0.15
Distance between anchor and fairlead (m)	6.97
Specimen stiffness of 0.4918 m (N/m)	740745
Elastic modulus (N/m ²)	7.72×10^{10}
Hydrodynamic equivalent diameter (m)	0.0052

The tests were performed in a flume called COCoTsu at IHCantabria. The flume is 56 m long, 2 m wide and 2.4 m high. It is equipped with a 2 m stroke piston-type paddle moved by a hydraulic actuator and includes an active wave absorption system. The testing area of this flume is 24 m long, with its sidewalls and bottom constructed of glass all along the testing section. A passive wave absorber built of vertical porous metal screens occupies the last 10 m of the wave flume. The models were placed according to Figure 1.

Figure 1. Side and plan views of flume and test mooring line locations

The objective of the laboratory tests was to simulate the mooring behaviour under different imposed movements, which are representative of floating offshore platform movements. These movements were reproduced by means of different actuators. A crankshaft with a pulley scheme was designed to recreate

the pitch movement. Meanwhile, surge and heave movements were reproduced with a linear actuator. All generated movements were sinusoidal. The capture of movements in the catenary shape was recorded using the underwater motion capture system Qualisys [28] through six markers along the mooring line separated 0.2 m from the fairlead. The mooring line loads were measured using axial load cells.

Different representative tests are selected to analyse and understand the limitations of simulation tools for the design of moorings. The study is focused on 2D movements: surge, heave and pitch. A total of twenty two tests are reproduced for the analysis and are summarised in Table 2. The table provides a description of the type of movement according to its degrees of freedom. Linear movements are defined by the amplitude and period, while rotational movements are defined by the radius and velocity. Measurements of the actuator feedback, the movements at six locations and the fairlead load are provided for each laboratory test. A set of tests are also reproduced with a sandy bed in order to evaluate the friction parameters in the different codes.

Table 2. Imposed movements (2D)

LINEAR MOVEMENTS			
Degree of Freedom		2AMPLITUDE (m)	PERIOD (s)
Surge	Model	0.250	0.79-1.58-2.37-3.16-4.74-6.32-7.91
	Prototype	10	5-10-15-20-30-40-50
Heave	Model	0.150	0.79-1.26-1.58-1.90-2.21-2.53-2.85-3.16-3.48
	Prototype	6	5-8-10-12-14-16-18-20-22
ROTATIONAL MOVEMENT			
Degree of Freedom		Radius (m)	Velocity (rad/s)
Pitch	Model	0.120	0.061-0.184-0.307-0.368-0.920-1.227
	Prototype	4.8	0.01-0.03-0.05-0.06-0.15-0.2

4. Parameters of the numerical model

A representative definition of the parameters involved in the prototype mooring system is required to obtain accurate design results. According to the numerical formulation presented in section 2, tension at the fairlead depends on many features of the mooring line and the floating structure motions caused by the environmental conditions. The numerical characteristics of the mooring line can be determined by means of 16 variables:

$$T = f[\rho_0, \rho_c, \rho_w, E, A, L, \beta, g, d, C_{DN}, C_{DT}, C_I, K_G, K_B, K_\mu, \text{discretisation elements}]$$

The characterisation of each variable can be achieved through a direct measurement (ρ_0, L), assuming universally accepted values (ρ_c, ρ_w, g), from calibration or direct measurement by means of tests (E, A, d, K_G, K_B, K_μ) and using guidelines or good practise standards ($\beta, C_{DN}, C_{DT}, C_I$, discretisation elements). In general, the mooring design parameters to be defined that require calibration are difficult to determine with precision in a real case, while the others can be defined with a relatively low design uncertainty. The definitions of the parameters subject to calibration are detailed in the following. Finally, all properties of the mooring line numerical model are presented in Table 3.

The resolution of numerical models assumes that the chain is a perfect cable as described in section 2.2. This hypothesis assumes an equivalent hydrodynamic diameter for the mooring line section. For this particular research piece, this parameter was obtained at the laboratory by means of water displacement tests, resulting in 0.0052 m.

The hydrodynamic coefficients are selected according to DNV [29] for a studless chain. This standard provides a normal drag coefficient value of 2.4 and a tangential value of 1.15, referring to the relative chain diameter. These values must be referred to the equivalent hydrodynamic diameter, resulting in values of 1.38 and 0.66, respectively. The added mass coefficient found in the guideline for a circular section is 1.

The axial stiffness used in this model, EA , is obtained through a tensile test. The definition of the different parameters of the mooring line – seabed contact model has been obtained for a rigid and a deformable seabed. The horizontal friction coefficient is obtained by means of a dragging test in the laboratory. The normal friction values, normal stiffness and normal damping, have been estimated by calibration between the numerical model and laboratory tests for each type of seabed. The calibration is carried out for an amplitude of 125 mm and a period of 1.58 s, with a validation for an amplitude of 125 mm and periods of 2.37 s and 3.16 s. The results of this calibration-validation are presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Calibration-validation mooring line – seabed contact model

Thirty-seven elements are used to discretise the mooring line according to the positions of the markers in the laboratory tests to exactly compare the movements measured with those estimated by the numerical model. A summary of all parameters involved in the numerical model is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Properties of mooring line numerical model

PROPERTIES	VALUES	SOURCE
Weight, ρ_0 (kg/m)	0.162	Direct measurement
Length, L (m)	7.305	Direct measurement
Hydrodynamic equivalent diameter, d (m)	0.0052	Laboratory measurement
Stiffness, EA (N)	364299	Laboratory measurement
Normal drag coefficient, C_{DN}	1.38	Standards
Tangential drag coefficient, C_{DT}	0.66	Standards
Added mass coefficient, C_I	1	Standards
Number of elements	37	Good practise
Structural damping, β (‰)	1	Good practise
Chain density, ρ_c (kg/m ³)	7850	Universal mean value
Water density, ρ_w (kg/m ³)	1000	Universal mean value
RIGID SEABED		
Normal stiffness, K_G (Pa/m)	300000	Laboratory calibration
Normal damping, K_B (Pa s/m)	20	Laboratory calibration
Tangential friction coefficient, K_μ	0.24	Laboratory calibration
DEFORMABLE SEABED		
Normal stiffness, K_G (Pa/m)	20000	Laboratory calibration
Normal damping, K_B (Pa s/m)	20	Laboratory calibration
Tangential friction coefficient, K_μ	0.7	Laboratory calibration

5. Numerical analysis

Normally, the mooring system design is a step by step process. First, a preliminary design is made taking the features of the floating platform together with the mooring system into account. Second, this design is validated based on physical model testing. This phase allows to highlight the need for improvements or even to provide a first optimisation of the mooring system. Finally, a calibrated numerical model is used to reproduce the tests of the previous phase and validate it. Laboratory tests simulate a limited number of metocean conditions of the floating platform and the mooring system. In general, they are representative of the Ultimate Limit State (ULS) and certain operational cases. Due to the limitations of laboratory tests, numerical modelling becomes an important design tool, especially for the Fatigue Limit State (FLS). The validation of numerical models and the importance of the mooring parameters in the design load are evaluated in this section.

5.1 Validation of numerical models

As has been previously stated, mooring numerical models are the base for mooring line design. In the present section, an exhaustive numerical model validation is summarised. An individualised analysis is conducted by analysing their capabilities and representing the mooring dynamics. Apart from this analysis, an aggregated analysis is also incorporated in order to give a general view of their accuracy. Once the influence of mooring design variables on the dynamics has been analysed, the accuracy of the numerical models described in section 2 is evaluated considering the parametrisation presented in Table 3. The validation is performed for a wide range of prescribed movements summarised in Table 2. The numerical models proposed predict the tension at the fairlead and the movements at the points measured in laboratory. The validation of the different numerical codes is performed through different steps. First, the static tension of numerical models is compared with the experiment for the different prescribed movements. Then, the results between the simulations and laboratory measurements of the tensions and motions in different points along the mooring line are presented for the different prescribed movements. These three parameters are crucial in a mooring line design.

5.1.1 Static tension

Table 4 shows the mean static tension of each prescribed movement for each numerical model and the experiment together with the error. The main differences are found in the quasi-static model. It shows a static tension below 2 % in surge and heave, reaching a difference of 3.77 % in pitch. Dynamic models

predict the static tension with a difference below 0.25 % in surge and heave being approximately 2 % in pitch.

Table 4. Comparison of static tension: numerical models & experiment

		QUASI-STATIC	DYNAMIC	DYNAMIC (APPROX.)	SESAM (DNV-GL)	EXPERIMENT
SURGE	TENSION (N)	5.99	5.89	5.89	5.89	5.89
	ERROR (%)	1.72	0.06	0.06	-0.06	-
HEAVE	TENSION (N)	5.94	5.84	5.84	5.83	5.83
	ERROR (%)	1.93	0.25	0.24	0.06	-
PITCH	TENSION (N)	6.33	6.23	6.23	6.22	6.10
	ERROR (%)	3.77	2.08	2.07	1.91	-

5.1.2 Dynamic tension and movements

Figure 3 and Figure 4 show comparisons between the simulated and measured tension series for prescribed surge movement, one with 1.58 s and another with 7.91 s. The accuracy of each numerical model is then presented by means of a percentage with respect to the experimental measures. Hence, positive percentages represent overestimated magnitudes and negative represent underestimated magnitudes. Dynamic models capture the tension wave shape and phases reasonably well. However, the numerical models proposed here are based on first-order, so the high-order harmonics generated by experimental tests with short periods of movement (1.58 s) are not reproduced properly. Nevertheless, a good agreement is found between the maximum and minimum tensions. Table 5 shows the difference percentage of the maximum tension between the different numerical models and the experimental model. Discrepancies below 3 % are found by the dynamic models in the prediction of maximum tensions.

Table 5. Error in the maximum tension prediction: numerical models & experiment.
Test: Surge (A = 125 mm, T = 1.58 s and 7.91 s)

SURGE		QUASI-STATIC	DYNAMIC	DYNAMIC (APPROX.)	SESAM (DNV-GL)
1.58 s	MAXIMUM	-32.25	0.10	1.43	-1.20
7.91 s	MAXIMUM	-0.19	-2.58	-2.33	-2.98

In contrast to the dynamic models, the quasi-static model is only able to accurately predict the tension series in movements with long periods, in which the influence of the dynamics is negligible. The maximum, minimum and phase tension are reproduced with an error below 0.2 %. The quasi-static model properly

estimates the response when the energy absorbed by the mooring line is negligible. This estimate happens when the displacement and the tension are in phase and, therefore, the maximum tension is coincident with the maximum amplitude. Instead, the dynamic effects on the moorings are visible when the hysteresis cycle contains an appreciable amount of energy dissipated. For this reason, dynamic effects on the tension are more severe in tests with short periods than long periods. The quasi-static model does not simulate the tension at the fairlead correctly in movements with a short period. The maximum tension is underestimated, and the minimum is overestimated. The tension time series appears out of phase with respect to the experimental measurement and the shape does not present wide troughs and pointed crests. The quasi-static response is in accordance with the fairlead position. Higher tensions are reached when the fairlead position is far from the anchor, while lower tensions appear when the fairlead is close to the anchor.

Figure 3. Validation of tension time series: numerical models & experiment. Test: Surge ($A = 125$ mm, $T = 1.58$ s)

Figure 4. Validation of tension time series: numerical models & experiment. Test: Surge ($A = 125$ mm, $T = 7.91$ s)

The ability of the different numerical models to capture the tension time series for the different movements proposed in Table 2 is presented in Figure 5 to Figure 7. The tension validation between the numerical and experimental models is described by several parameters: the maximum, minimum, amplitude and mean. For each parameter, the results provided by each numerical model are represented against the experimental results. If numerical and experimental results are coincident, they will be represented by a point in the bisector of the graph. In contrast, if they are not coincident, they will be far of the bisector. A greater distance from the bisector indicates a higher inaccuracy on the tension numerical prediction. The dynamic model results present a good agreement against the experimental results in all movements. The predicted maximum tensions are below 4 % with respect to the experimental tension in surge and heave movements, while they are under 1.5 % in the pitch movement. The amplitude estimation presents a good correlation with experimental tests, showing values over the bisector in all degrees of freedom. The mean tension is predicted with differences below 2.5 %. In general, the response of the dynamic models is in accordance with experimental tests, except for the tests with snap tensions. Two tests with snap tensions are detected in the experimental collection: one in surge and another in heave. Both happen for a period of 0.79 s. As it has been commented on in previous sections, snap tensions are generated by slack events and cause higher peak tensions on the mooring line. Not all models under snap conditions properly reproduce the maximum tension. Snap conditions are represented on the maximum tension graph for surge and heave movements as outliers with respect to the bisector. Dynamic models present discrepancies below 23 % and 12 % in the evaluation of this tension. The prediction of this type of loads requires advances techniques,

such as that proposed by [11] based on a discontinuous Galerkin method including a Riemann solver built using the local Lax-Friedrich flux. A quasi-static model only estimates the tension properly in longer periods. Remarkable differences can be observed in the maximum, minimum and amplitude tension for the most dynamic periods. Higher discrepancies are found in surge and heave movements than those in pitch movements. Pitch experimental tests only consider relatively long periods. In this way, the maximum tension discrepancy is approximately 32 % for the surge tests with a period of 1.58 s or 16 % for the heave test with a period of 1.26 s. The rest of the period collection shows differences below 6 %. All pitch tests are reproduced according to experimental tests with discrepancies below 1.5 %. The snap events are not estimated accurately, and the quasi-static tension is four times less than the experimental tests in surge and two times less in heave.

Figure 5. Validation of tension time series: numerical models & experiment. Test: Surge ($A = 125$ mm)
 Numerical models: quasi-static model (\circ), dynamic model ($*$), dynamic model (approx.) (\blacktriangleright), Sesam (DNV-GL) (\times)

Figure 6. Validation of tension time series: numerical models & experiment. Test: Heave ($A = 75$ mm)
 Numerical models: quasi-static model (\circ), dynamic model ($*$), dynamic model (approx.) (\blacktriangleright), Sesam (DNV-GL) (\times)

Figure 7. Validation of tension time series: numerical models & experiment. Test: Pitch (Radii = 120 mm)
 Numerical models: quasi-static model (○), dynamic model (*), dynamic model (approx.) (▴), Sesam (DNV-GL) (×)

Movements in six different points are measured during all experimental tests. However, only two points are analysed here: Point 2 and Point 4. These points are located from fairlead at 0.4 m and 0.8 m, respectively, and are selected because Point 2 presents movements of the same order of magnitude in the x-direction and the z-direction while Point 4 has a predominate movement in z-direction, being neglected in x-direction. Figure 8 to Figure 11 present comparisons between the simulated and measured displacement time series for surge prescribed tests in the x-direction and the z-direction for periods of 1.58 s and 7.91 s. In general, dynamic models reasonably predict the motions. Phases are captured according to the experiment, although slight differences are found in the prediction of the maximum and minimum. Nevertheless, the agreement is still good. The shape of displacement wave is reproduced perfectly for 7.91 s. However, some uncertainties in the prediction of the displacement time series shape induced by high order harmonics in shorter periods can clearly be seen in the vertical displacements (Figure 9). The quasi-static model predicts movements out of phase in tests with shorter periods (1.58 s), while they are in phase for longer periods (7.91 s). A good correlation is obtained in the movement estimation of the maximum and minimum amplitude in longer periods, showing more inaccuracies in shorter periods in comparison with dynamic models and experimental results because these methods cannot reproduce high-order movements.

Figure 8. Validation of displacement time series in the x-direction for Point 2: numerical models & experiment
 Test: Surge ($A = 125 \text{ mm}$, $T = 1.58 \text{ s}$)

Figure 9. Validation of displacement time series in the z-direction for Point 2: numerical models & experiment
 Test: Surge ($A = 125 \text{ mm}$, $T = 1.58 \text{ s}$)

Figure 10. Validation of displacement time series in the x-direction for Point 4: numerical models & experiment.
Test: Surge ($A = 125$ mm, $T = 7.91$ s)

Figure 11. Validation of displacement time history in the z-direction for Point 4: numerical models & experiment.
Test: Surge ($A = 125$ mm, $T = 7.91$ s)

The capability of the numerical models to reproduce the movements in the x-direction and the z-direction using Points 2 and 4 is summarised in Figure 12 to Figure 15. The numerical model validation is performed by comparing the maximum, minimum and amplitude of displacement for all tests against the experimental results. In general, dynamic models predict the movements reasonably well in all directions. The predicted maximum movements in the x-direction of Points 2 and 4 show an absolute error below 0.005 m with respect to experimental case, although it is higher in snap events reaching 0.02 m. An absolute error below 0.01 m is obtained by numerical models in the estimation of the maximum movements in the z-direction. The minimum displacements present discrepancies lower down than 0.006 m in the x-direction,

being slightly higher in the z-direction of up to 0.012 m. As in the maximum tension evaluation, experimental tests involving snap conditions increase the error up to 0.04 m in the z-direction. More pronounced differences are estimated by the quasi-static model. Short period tests show a difference below 0.013 m and 0.04 m in the estimation of the maximum and minimum movement in the z-direction, respectively. However, a good agreement is achieved for the rest of the experimental tests with differences lower than 0.006 m for movements in the x- and z-directions. On average, the relative error of the dynamic model is below 9 %.

Figure 12. Validation of displacement time histories in the x-direction for Point 2: numerical models & experiment.
 Test: Surge ($A = 125$ mm).
 Numerical models: quasi-static model (○), dynamic model (*), dynamic model (approx.) (▴), Sesam (DNV-GL) (×)

Figure 13. Validation of displacement time histories in the z-direction for Point 2: numerical models & experiment.
 Test: Surge ($A = 125$ mm).
 Numerical models: quasi-static model (○), dynamic model (*), dynamic model (approx.) (▴), Sesam (DNV-GL) (×)

Figure 14. Validation of displacement time histories in the x-direction for Point 4: numerical models & experiment.
 Test: Surge ($A = 125$ mm).
 Numerical models: quasi-static model (\circ), dynamic model ($*$), dynamic model (approx.) (\blacktriangleright), Sesam (DNV-GL) (\times)

Figure 15. Validation of displacement time histories in the z-direction for Point 4: numerical models & experiment.
 Tests: Surge ($A = 125$ mm).
 Numerical models: quasi-static model (\circ), dynamic model ($*$), dynamic model (approx.) (\blacktriangleright), Sesam (DNV-GL) (\times)

5.2 Sensitivity of the parameters involved in the prediction of mooring loads

This section attempts to highlight the main uncertainties associated with the mooring design variables. The purpose is to analyse if the parameterization, given in Table 3, properly represents the mooring behaviour and to identify the most critical parameters in its definition. A sensitivity study is performed to determine the most significant mooring parameters over the numerical outcomes, using laboratory tests as a reference. The analysis is conducted in a manner where the target mooring parameter changes according to a percentage from a reference value, while the other parameters remain constant according to Table 3. The impact of the following parameters on the tension at the fairlead is investigated: mooring line discretisation, structural damping, drag coefficient, hydrodynamic mass coefficient, stiffness, weight-diameter, friction coefficients, and length. The range of variation used for each parameter in this study is shown in Table 6 with the first column indicating the reference parameter. The parametric variation selected

is between $\pm 50\%$ of the reference value except for structural damping and length due to their high impact over the results.

Table 6. Mooring parametric variation

PARAMETERS	ELEMENTS																		
	37	10	15	19	26	30	33	34	35	36	38	39	40	41	44	48	56		
NUMERICAL	STRUCTURAL DAMPING: β																		
	0.001	0.0001	0.0003	0.0005	0.0007	0.0013	0.0015	0.0017	0.003	0.005	0.007	0.01	0.03	0.05	0.07	0.1			
	DRAG COEFFICIENT: C_{DN}, C_{DT}																		
	1.38	0.69	0.97	1.10	1.24	1.28	1.31	1.34	1.37	1.39	1.42	1.45	1.48	1.52	1.66	1.79	2.07		
	0.66	0.33	0.46	0.53	0.59	0.61	0.63	0.64	0.65	0.67	0.68	0.69	0.71	0.73	0.79	0.86	0.99		
	MASS COEFFICIENT: C_I																		
	1.00	1.01	1.02	1.03	1.05	1.07	1.09	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.5	1.6	1.7	1.8	1.9	2		
	STIFFNESS: EA (N)																		
	364299	182150	255009	291439	327869	338798	346084	353370	360656	367942	375228	382514	389800	400729	437159	473589	546449		
	WEIGHT: ρ_0 (kg/m) - DIAMETER: d (m)																		
	0.162	0.081	0.113	0.130	0.146	0.151	0.154	0.157	0.160	0.164	0.167	0.170	0.173	0.178	0.194	0.211	0.243		
	0.0052	0.0036	0.0043	0.0046	0.0049	0.0049	0.0050	0.0050	0.0051	0.0052	0.0052	0.0053	0.0053	0.0054	0.0056	0.0059	0.0063		
	FRICTION COEFFICIENTS: K_G (Pa/m), K_B (Pa s/m), K_μ																		
	300000	150000	210000	240000	270000	279000	285000	291000	297000	303000	309000	315000	321000	330000	360000	390000	450000		
	20	10	14	16	18	19	19	19	20	20	21	21	21	22	24	26	30		
	0.24	0.12	0.17	0.19	0.22	0.22	0.23	0.23	0.24	0.24	0.25	0.25	0.26	0.26	0.29	0.31	0.36		
LENGHT: L (m)																			
7.305	7.25	7.26	7.27	7.28	7.29	7.30	7.31	7.32	7.33	7.34	7.35								

The numerical model used in this parametric study is the dynamic model with the tridiagonal matrix approximation. Numerical models based on the Finite Element Method need to define a number of elements to discretise the mooring line and solve the equation presented in (2) with a higher computational cost. A sensitivity analysis is performed using different numbers of elements to investigate this effect. The maximum (T_{max}) and minimum (T_{min}) tensions are compared for three different prescribed movements in surge. The parametric results show that not relevant changes are found in the tension from the nineteen elements in comparison with the laboratory results, as displayed in Figure 16. Another numerical parameter analysed here is the structural damping coefficient. A set of different values is proposed to determinate an adjustment range of this parameter. Figure 16 shows that the best tension fit is achieved with coefficients between 1‰ – 2‰ according to the experimental results.

Figure 16. Variations in tension due to the number of elements and structural damping for different prescribed movements in surge

In general, the Froude scaling law is selected in laboratory tests because this scale is the most suitable for simulating the floating platform hydrodynamic loads. This type of scale properly represents the restoring force, the weight and the inertia loads of the mooring system. However, drag loads are also significant on moorings and should be considered for simulating mooring dynamics. For this reason, dynamic scaling schemes have been proposed [30] and require that a series of non-dimensional numbers must be equal between the model and prototype. These requirements tend to be quite demanding with the characteristics of the experimental setup, which means that the Froude scaling law is followed in most cases despite being incorrect with the Reynolds number.

The influence of the drag coefficient on the tension at the fairlead is presented in Figure 17 for prescribed movements in surge. Three different periods for each prescribed movement at the fairlead are simulated. The line called “LABORATORY” is the tension obtained by means of experimental tests. The purpose of this figure is to highlight the variations in tension due to the different drag coefficients and the importance of fixing a representative value in the numerical model. The maximum tension (T_{max}) and the minimum tension (T_{min}) are shown for different tangential and normal drag coefficients. Simulations simultaneously take the variation of normal and tangential drag coefficients into account, so they are not considered individually. However, the results are shown in different figures to more clearly appreciate the effects of these parameters on the mooring line tension. Movements with low periods (1.58 s and 2.37 s) at the fairlead show a strong dependence of the drag coefficient on the mooring tension due to the higher

velocities generated by these movements in the mooring line. If the drag coefficient is underestimated, the maximum and the minimum tensions are also underestimated, and vice versa. In contrast, movements with long periods (7.91 s) make the maximum and minimum tensions coincide with the experimental results independent of the drag coefficient via the small influence of the velocity in the movement.

Figure 17. Variations in tension using different drag coefficients for different prescribed movements in surge

The variations in the maximum and minimum tension (%) due to the selection of the drag coefficient with respect to the laboratory tension are shown in Figure 18 for prescribed movements in surge, heave and pitch. The percentage of the maximum tension is represented by circles, while the minimum is represented by squares. All prescribed movements with their different periods are shown together with the drag coefficients selected in each simulation. Since the different prescribed movements do not have the same periods, it is not possible to compare results between the degrees of freedom. However, if analysing the mooring behaviour according to the different types of selected movements, the most significant variations are found in lower periods, particularly in 1.26 s, 1.58 s and 2.37 s by the higher velocities on the movements. The rest of the simulated cases registered differences below 4 %. In general, the low periods require selecting an appropriate drag coefficient to obtain a representative tension of the tested mooring system. Thus, drag coefficients similar to the laboratory model show differences below 2 %, while remote values, show differences of up to 30 %, reaching tensions of almost double that for the lower drag coefficients. Finally, it should be noted that the Reynolds number is not captured properly in the

experimental tests because the Froude scale is used. However, the range of Reynolds numbers in the prescribed movement of experimental tests is between 400 and 5000. A normal drag coefficient of 2.4 is selected for all tests, although the drag coefficient changes according to the Reynolds number. The standards do not clearly reflect this fact in the case of chains [34]. They define limits; for example, the drag coefficient is between 2.1 and 2.7 for a Reynolds number between 1400 and 10000. This number is remarkable, and a more detailed study of the drag coefficient for a circular cylinder given in [33]. The drag coefficient can change up to 50 % when the Reynolds number has a variation of 30000 to 80000, although this study is referred to as steady flow and not oscillatory flow.

Figure 18. Variations in tension (%) with respect to the reference configuration due to the drag coefficients: maximum tension (●) and minimum tension (■)

The importance of the hydrodynamic mass coefficient on the tension is evaluated considering values of added mass coefficient between 1 and 2 according to [33]. Figure 19 shows the results obtained for the different prescribed movements in surge. This figure shows that the variations in the hydrodynamic mass coefficient do not have an important impact on the tension at the fairlead. Inertial effects are negligible on the moorings due to its relative size.

The axial stiffness of the mooring line is assessed by means of a tensile test. However, tensile tests are not always available in laboratory tests and sometimes the stiffness has to be estimated using expressions that relate the stiffness to the link diameter of the mooring line [19]. The stiffness parametric analysis

incorporates ranges of stiffness similar to the one provided by these expressions. Figure 19 indicates that these expressions can be an excellent approximation for obtaining the stiffness in the absence of tensile tests because significant differences are not appreciated in the tension at the fairlead by variation in the stiffness in comparison with the experimental tests. Despite this approximation, it should be noted that the stiffness governs the mooring line behaviour in presence of snap tensions, as discussed below.

Figure 19. Variations in tension due to the hydrodynamic mass coefficient and the stiffness for different prescribed movements in surge

The weight provides the restoring force in a catenary mooring system and, therefore, it determines the response of a floating structure and the tension on the mooring line. The weight is related to the chain diameter dimensions. In general, more weight implicates a higher diameter. Numerical models solve the equation of mooring governance by similitude to a cable; the tension analysis due to weight variations implicates adopting a hydrodynamic equivalent diameter according to the weight. Different cases of the weight-diameter are proposed in Table 6 for evaluating the tension differences by an inaccuracy definition of these parameters with respect to the laboratory case. Figure 20 shows the influence of the weight over the dynamic tension for different prescribed movements in surge and pitch. Higher tensions are found for higher weights and short periods of movement. It should be noted that the tension variations due to the weight present a similar slope for intermediate-long periods, while it is higher in short periods according to the surge movement. However, the tension variations are coincident, conforming to the pitch movement for the longest movement period. Therefore, the importance of the mooring weight is higher under the

prescribed dynamic movements. These results are a consequence of the importance of the inertia of the mooring line and the drag forces generated by the fairlead movement. Intermediate-short period movements generate important drag forces, while they are negligible in long period movements. It is concluded that the tension variations are directly proportional to the weight and the evaluated prescribed movement. In view of the results obtained, it is crucial to adequately characterise the weight in laboratory tests to achieve a good agreement with the tensions estimated by means of numerical models.

The weight measured in the laboratory is 0.162 kg/m. The percentage of the tension variation for the different prescribed movements considered as a consequence of the weight-equivalent diameter variation is exposed in Figure 21. According to this figure, weights between 0.146 kg/m and 0.178 kg/m are shown to have differences below 11 % for the maximum tension with respect to the reference weight.

Figure 20. Variations in tension due to the weight for different prescribed movements in surge and pitch

Figure 21. Variations in tension (%) with respect to the reference configuration due to the different mooring weights: maximum tension (●) and minimum tension (■)

The interaction between the mooring line and the seabed is defined through the friction coefficients in the numerical models as have been exposed in section 2.2. The interactions between the mooring line and the seabed are simulated with a spring-damper model, representing the vertical reaction and a tangential friction model as a horizontal reaction. Constants, K_G , K_B and K_μ represent the stiffness, viscous damping and kinetic friction coefficients, in the contact model respectively. Different coefficients are proposed in Table 3 depending on the type of seabed, distinguishing between a rigid and deformable seabed. Here, the variability of the tension only considering a rigid seabed is analysed because, in general, the laboratory tests in a wave basin for a prototype of a floating structure do not use a mobile bathymetry. The influence of the contact model coefficients on the maximum and minimum tension is displayed in Figure 22 for different prescribed movements in surge. The parametric variation considers different coefficients for each parameter at the same time. K_G is represented by the x-axis, K_μ is defined by the bars on the right y-axis of the graph and K_B with a number inside the bars. The combination of these three parameters provides a tension shown on the left y-axis. The results reveal that variations of up to 50 % in the reference friction parameters do not generate appreciable changes in the tension at the fairlead. Similar results are obtained for the heave and pitch prescribed movements.

Figure 22. Variations in tension due to the friction coefficients for different prescribed movements in surge

Length is a key parameter in the determination of the mooring line behaviour. If the design considers the possibility of completely stretched lines or snap events, the stiffness will also have an important role in the evaluation of the mooring line tension. The length of the lifted mooring line determines the mooring pretension, which also drives the dynamic performance of the mooring and is highly sensitive to the line length. Figure 23 shows the pretension variability due to mooring line length. A variation below 1 % of reference length may increase the reference pretension up to 1.4 times. Figure 24a denotes the variations in the tension due to the length considering the experimental stiffness measured by tensile tests. This figure, which is based on surge prescribed movement tests, reveals that the length has an important impact on the tension, above all in short periods. The reference length in the experiment is 7.305 m and variations of 0.005 m (0.07 %) with respect to the aforementioned length can generate up to a 6.5 % of difference in the maximum tension. Higher discrepancies are obtained with variations of 0.055 m (0.75 %), reaching tensions of two times the reference tension for periods of 1.58 s and 2.37 s. The percentage of tension differences with respect to the reference situation is shown in Figure 24b for surge, heave and pitch movements. The shorter the mooring line is, the higher tensions are and vice versa in all prescribed movements. Length differences lower than 0.7 % with respect to the experimental length can cause tensions of up to twice the laboratory tension in all degrees of freedom. Therefore, an accurate length definition is fundamental for evaluating the mooring behaviour correctly. This is a very important conclusion with special relevance for sea trials or future floating offshore wind structures, where limited water depths combined with large

excursions and the limited accuracy on mooring line length definition may contribute to unexpected mooring line loads.

Figure 23. Pretension variation due to the mooring line length

Figure 24. a) Variations in tension due to the length for different prescribed movements in surge. b) Variations in tension (%) with respect to the reference configuration due to the length for different degrees of freedom: maximum tension (●) and minimum tension (■)

The downscaled mooring setups need to reproduce all mechanics and physical characteristics at a laboratory scale. Notwithstanding that the majority of properties can be reproduced properly, the stiffness is a special case in the catenary configuration. The parameter that dominates the behaviour of a catenary is the weight. For this reason, the chain selected for laboratory scale, which is usually a commercial chain, has to meet this requirement. Frequently, the commercial chains used in laboratory present a higher stiffness

in comparison with the scaled real stiffness. Traditionally, this problem has been solved by means of springs. The deficient tank water depth is solved by a truncation method, which is also based on inclusions of springs on the line [32]. Mooring truncation is a method to test floating platforms in deep and ultra-deep waters when the wave basin is not sufficiently deep to represent the real depth. This new configuration of mooring solves the problem related to the depth and the stiffness by reproducing the displacement-force curve by means of springs. However, when the wave basin has a suitable depth frequently in shallow and intermediate waters it is not common to make a truncation. In this case, the catenary loads could present some uncertainties associated with the stiffness. Table 7 compares the stiffness obtained by following the guidelines in DNV [31] using a studless chain R5 and tensile tests. It should be noted that the prototype has a value of EA one order of magnitude less than that of the experimental model. The implications of these stiffnesses on the tension at the fairlead are shown in Figure 25 and Table 8. Three different prescribed movements at the fairlead with different periods are simulated using the prototype and the experimental stiffness. The results are evidence that the stiffness has an important role in the mooring behaviour when slack events are produced in the line followed by snap loads during reengagement. A higher stiffness generates more critical design loads. Differences below 19 % are found when the two stiffness are compared. For this reason, although the weight in a catenary is a key parameter for defining its behaviour, other parameters should be analysed carefully, such as the stiffness. A good definition of snap loads is required because of reducing the fatigue life on a mooring system and, generally, the experimental model is often not representative of the prototype in this type of phenomena.

Table 7. Stiffness comparison between prototype and experimental model

PROTOTYPE		EXPERIMENTAL MODEL	
Link diameter (mm)	120	Link diameter (mm)	3
E (N/m²) – R5	5.614E+10	EA (N)	364299
EA (N)	1291220000		
EA (N) 1:40 (Froude scaling)	20176		

Figure 25. Tension comparisons using the experimental and prototype stiffness for surge prescribed movements with different periods

Table 8. Difference (%) in tension at the fairlead obtained for the experimental model & prototype

MOVEMENT	PERIOD (s)	EXPERIMENTAL (N)	PROTOTYPE (N)	DIFFERENCE (%)
SURGE	0.79	32.21	27.15	18.64
	1.58	20.30	18.36	10.57
	2.37	14.78	13.91	6.25
	7.91	13.28	12.92	2.79
HEAVE	1.26	8.34	8.22	1.36
	2.53	6.79	6.65	2.18
	3.48	6.76	6.62	2.12
PITCH	5.12	24.19	22.25	8.72
	17.07	23.72	21.87	8.46
	102.40	23.99	22.11	8.50

6. Conclusions

Mooring system modelling depends on many design parameters. The scaling of these parameters from the prototype to the experimental model may not represent the reality given by the prototype. Hence, simulating a mooring system on a small scale tests implicates assuming different uncertainties between the prototype and the experimental model. The main uncertainties are related to the drag forces because the Reynolds number is not well reproduced at the laboratory scale. Moreover, the stiffness at the laboratory

scale is generally higher than the prototype stiffness, which may lead to higher mooring loads. Therefore, the experimental model requires an accurate characterisation to be able to successfully replicate the experimental tests with numerical models.

An exhaustive sensitive study is performed with the purpose of assessing the variation in tension at the fairlead due to inaccuracies in the definition of mooring design parameters. From the reference configuration tested in laboratory, the loads are analysed according to the main parameters that govern the behaviour of the mooring system.

First, the effects of different numerical parameters on the response of the mooring are analysed. Taking into account the fact that numerical models based on the Finite Element Method require a number of elements to solve the mooring dynamics equation, a parametric study is conducted to explore its potential effects on the tension estimation. Values from nineteen elements show a good correlation with the experimental load results with differences below of 2.5 %. Another important numerical parameter is the damping coefficient. The damping coefficient contributes to the numerical stability and, according to the experimental tests, the best fit is achieved with coefficients between 1 ‰ and 2 ‰.

Second, the importance of different parameters related to the forces on the mooring are investigated. The type of seabed (rigid or deformable) has relevance in the determination of friction coefficients. However, once the type of seabed is known, the variability in the friction coefficients have a minor importance on the mooring system response in consonance with the simulated cases. The impact of the inertial force on the dynamics is evaluated considering different hydrodynamic mass coefficients. The results show that inertial effects are negligible. In contrast, drag forces present an appreciable influence in the dynamic movement tests. In particular, variations in the reference drag coefficient below 50 % can generate differences of up to 30 % on mooring loads. Since the mooring weight depends on the diameter, the influence of the weight and diameter on the dynamics is jointly analysed. The results reveal that the weight-diameter has influence over moorings independent of the prescribed movement. Discrepancies of 10 % with respect to the reference weight-diameter show differences below 11 % on loads. Simulations show a considerable sensitivity by small variations of length. Variations lower than 1 % generate loads of up to twice the experimental loads. In general, the mooring stiffness has a secondary role with respect to the weight. Nonetheless, it plays a key role in the snap events. In these situations, it completely governs the mooring behaviour. The importance in stiffness during snap events is analysed considering the prototype and experimental model. Load differences of up to 19 % are obtained when the two stiffness are compared.

Finally, the ability of the numerical models to reproduce the mooring behaviour in terms of tensions and movements is presented. In general, a good accuracy is achieved between the numerical and experimental results. Dynamic models evidence a good estimation of tensions and movements except in snap conditions where errors of up to 23 % are detected. The quasi-static model is only a good estimation of mooring loads when the energy dissipated by the hysteresis cycle is essentially negligible.

Acknowledgements

The authors acknowledge the financial support from the Spanish Ministry of Economy, Industry and Competitiveness to the PhD candidate Carlos Barrera Sánchez through his research training scholarship. Grant Agreement no. BES-2014-070381. This work is part of two research projects: i) VAPEO - Influencia de la Variabilidad climática del océano sobre la Producción de Energía de las Olas (grant agreement no. ENE2013-48716-R within National Programme for Research Aimed at the Challenges of Society, call 2013) and ii) ACOPLÉ - Análisis del Comportamiento dinámico de Plataformas Eólicas flotantes para la optimización del diseño de aguas profundas (grant agreement no. ENE2017-89716-R within the National Programme for Research, Development and Innovation Aimed at the Challenges of Society, call 2017). Raúl Guanche also acknowledges financial support from the Ramon y Cajal Program (RYC-2017-23260) of the Spanish Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities.

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